

Halogenation. Part VII. Iodination and Bromination of Naphthalene and β -Naphthol.

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Iodonaphthalene is not ordinarily obtained by direct iodination and the yield obtained by the methods already known is very poor. Noelting (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 135) obtained this compound by digesting α -naphthalene diazonium sulphate with potassium iodide in an acid solution. Otto and Mörtes (*Annalen*, 1868, 147, 173) obtained iodonaphthalene by the action of iodine on a solution of mercuri-di- α -naphthyl in carbon disulphide. Edinger and Goldberg (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2882) prepared this compound along with β -iodonaphthalene by the action of sulphur iodide and excess of nitric acid on naphthalene in light petroleum at 100° for several hours. Datta and Chatterji (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 435) obtained a mixture of iodo- and mononitronaphthalenes by the action of iodine in presence of concentrated nitric acid.

Attempts have been made in these experiments to iodinate naphthalene under different conditions and the best yield is obtained by iodinating in presence of a mixture of nitrosulphonic acid and fuming nitric acid.

Iodo- β -naphthol has been obtained by Meldola (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1885, 47, 525) by adding iodine to an acetic acid solution of β -naphthol, sodium acetate and lead acetate. Lepetit (*Gazzetta*, 1890, 20, 107) seems to have obtained this compound by the action of nitrogen iodide on β -naphthol dissolved in caustic soda. Monoiodo derivative of β -naphthol has now been obtained by iodinating β -naphthol in presence of a number of reagents, but the best yield is obtained in presence of ammonium hydroxide. The nascent nitrogen iodide formed by the action of iodine on ammonium hydroxide seems to be the active iodinating agent in this case.

Naphthalene is more readily brominated and if bromination is carried on in presence of substances like mixture of fuming nitric and nitrosulphonic acids, not only a very good yield of the bromo derivatives is obtained, but there is also no evolution of hydrobromic

acid at all, thus avoiding the wastage of bromine in the form of hydrobromic acid.

β -Naphthol has been directly brominated before and a number of bromo derivatives have been obtained (Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1879, 35, 789; Armstrong, *Chem. News*, 1889, 59, 225; 1891, 63, 136; Felensa, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1480). The best yield of the bromo derivatives is, however, obtained when bromination is carried on at low temperatures, preferably at 10°, in presence of a third substance such as concentrated or fuming sulphuric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Iodination of naphthalene.—Naphthalene, iodine and glacial acetic acid were heated in a flask on a sand-bath, provided with a reflux condenser. Nitrosulphonic acid mixture (equal quantities of fuming nitric acid and nitrosulphonic acid) was then dropped little at a time from the top of the condenser. When the whole of the acid mixture was added, the contents of the flask were heated for some specified period, at the end of which they were boiled with animal charcoal (1—2 g.), filtered and concentrated to a smaller volume. The liquid obtained was then distilled under reduced pressure on a paraffin bath. Iodine and acetic acid were then distilled off and the residue containing the iodo derivative was extracted with benzene and the benzene distilled off. A liquid boiling at 302–305° was thus obtained. It gave naphthalene when boiled with alcoholic potash and formed golden yellow needles of picrate, m.p. 127°. It is therefore α -iodonaphthalene.

In a few cases, it has been found equally convenient to pour the whole of the reaction product into a large quantity of water when the heavy layer of the iodo compound settles at the bottom. It is then separated in a tap funnel, washed several times with 10% potassium hydroxide, then with water, dried by means of anhydrous calcium chloride and distilled. The experiments are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Naphthalene = 10 g.

Iodine.	The third substance used.	Reaction period.	Yield of iodo-naphthalene.
5 g.	Potassium persulphate (5 g.)	9 hr.	3.2 g.
5	Chromic acid (5 g.)	1½	3.4
6	{ Fuming sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) { Fuming nitric acid (5 c.c.)	9	4.0

TABLE I (contd.).

Iodine.	The third substance used.	Reaction period.	Yield of iodo-naphthalene.
6 g.	Strong nitric acid (5 c.c.)	2½ hr.	3·6 g.
6	Fuming nitric acid (5 c.c.)	2½	3·7
6	Nitrosulphonic acid mixture (5 c.c.)	2½	4·2
10	Nitrosulphonic acid mixture (15 c.c.)	1½	6·2
	Glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.)		

Iodination of β -naphthol.—A better yield of iodo- β -naphthol than what was obtained by Meldola (*loc. cit.*) was obtained by iodinating β -naphthol by means of iodine dissolved in KI solution in presence of ammonia. For this purpose, β -naphthol (5 g.) was dissolved in concentrated ammonia (10 c.c.) and iodine (4·5 g.) in KI solution was then added drop by drop and shaken. When the whole of the iodine solution was added, the product was poured into dilute sulphuric acid when a flocculent white precipitate was obtained. This crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 93-94°, yield 9·2 g.

Bromination of Naphthalene.—Naphthalene (10 g.) dissolved in carbon tetrachloride, was refluxed on a water-bath. Bromine (2 c.c.) dissolved in the same solvent was then added drop by drop. When the whole of the bromine was added, the third substance (if any) was then dropped little at a time and the whole of these operations took about an hour. The contents of the flask were then heated on a sand-bath to drive off the solvent, the residue extracted with dilute alcohol. On standing, the extract separated into two layers. The lower layer was separated; washed with dilute alcohol, dehydrated over calcium chloride and distilled. The fraction distilling at 283°-285° was found to be monobromo derivative.

If the product contains a nitro derivative also, the nitro derivative separates out in a crystalline form from the alcoholic extract and is separated and purified. The results are summarised in Table II.

Bromination of β -naphthol.— β -Naphthol (5 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.), was put into a flask, immersed in a thermostat at 10° and bromine (1·8 c.c.) dissolved in acetic acid (15 c.c.) was added to it drop by drop from a tap funnel and the flask was shaken after each addition. When the whole of the bromine solution was added the flask was allowed to stand for about an hour in the thermostat and then the contents poured into a porcelain dish and allowed

to stand for about 12 hours, when long light-brown needles separated out. By repeated crystallisation from acetic acid or from petroleum ether in which the bromo compounds are soluble, fine shining crystals of 1-bromo- β -naphthol (m.p. 83-84°) or of 1:6-dibromo- β -naphthol (m.p. 105-06°) were obtained. The results are summarised in Table III with 5 g. of β -naphthol, the time allowed for the reaction being 1½ hours in each case, in the last case bromine added being 3.6 c.c.

TABLE II.

Third substance used.	Yield of monobromo naphthalene.
...	3.4 g. (21%)
Aluminium-mercury couple (2 g.)	4.5 g. (28%)
Strong nitric acid (5 c.c.)	4.5 g. (36%)
Fuming nitric acid (5 c.c.)	7.6 g. (47%) also mono-nitro-naphthalene (2 g.)
Nitro sulphonic acid mixture (5 c.c.)	10.1 g. (62%) also mono-nitronaphthalene (3 g.)

TABLE III.

Third substance used.	Yield.
Diffused sunlight	1-Bromo- β -naphthol (5.6 g.)
Strong sulphuric acid (1 c.c.)	1-Bromo- β -naphthol (5.8 g.)
Fuming sulphuric acid (1 c.c.)	1-Bromo- β -naphthol (6.5 g.)
Aluminium-mercury couple (1.5 g.)	1-bromo- β -naphthol (3.8 g.)
Fuming sulphuric acid. (1 c.c.)	1:6 Dibromo- β -naphthol (3.5 g.)

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